

Mechanical Testing and Micrographic Examination of Prepreg GFRP Composites with Different Pressure-Temperature Cycles

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ABSTRACT

Glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites with different fibre orientations and various pressure - temperature cycles have been studied in order to establish the influence of fabrication cycle on the properties of the material. Tensile tests and micrographic examinations were carried out and their results have been comparatively analysed. It is shown that simple tensile tests do not point out meaningful differences between laminates with same fibre orientations but different cure cycles, whereas micrographic examination indicates decisively different porosity contents. Such structural variations influence undoubtedly the composite dynamic or corrosion resistance and must therefore be determined either through time consuming techniques, like microscopy or fatigue and corrosion testing, or through a rather simple and real time technique, like acoustic emission testing.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years the employment of semimanufactured materials, like unidirectional or fabric prepregs where fibres and resin distribution uniformity is assured within restricted limits, has considerably increased. The results expected and actually obtained were a higher reliability of the final products and a much lesser dispersion in the material properties.

Anyway the employment of prepregs is not sufficient to avoid the possibility of dispersion in the properties of a composite component if the limits of variation of the fabrication cycle parameters are not accurately specified. As a matter of fact fibres and resin uniformity does not influence other important factors affecting the final material properties such as void content and resin curing.

The principal aim of the present work is the observation of the possible mechanical and micrographic variations induced by different fabrication cycles in prepreg GFRP composite samples with diverse orientations. The examined orientations have been restricted to 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ in order to analyse simple laminates

and to directly correlate the experimental results of the fabrication conditions.
 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material used in this study was a Crowfoot Satin glass fibre fabric from GI.VI.DI. (Brugherio - Milan) obtained as prepreg with isophthalic polyester resin. This material, commercially designated with VR 34 P (U.S.A.: 143 - 150) has 90% of the reinforcement in the warp direction and 10% in the weft direction. Fabric weight is 305 g/m² and the resin weight content in the prepreg is about 38%.

In order to study the influence of the variation of cure cycle parameters (pressure - temperature - time) on the behaviour of the material, two types of laminate, both obtained by superimposing 8 prepreg laminae, were fabricated: the first with warp (90% of reinforcement) oriented in the 0° direction and the second with warp in the ±45° direction. All laminates were symmetric and equilibrated.

The choice of these two orientations is due to the different fracture modes operating in the two different laminates (1). In 0° laminates, whose resistance is almost uniquely dependent on the longitudinal fibres strength, σ_1 has the obvious responsibility for the final failure. In ±45° laminates both σ_2 and τ_{12} are significantly present: therefore the composite resistance relies on the tensile and shear strength of the matrix and fibre-matrix interface, whereas σ_1 attains a practically negligible value.

In table I the parameters of the different cure cycles taken into consideration are summarized. In figure 1 the graphs of temperature and pressure as functions of time are schematically reported. More details on the adopted cure cycles are in (2).

One or two ±45° laminates were prepared for each cure cycle, whereas two 0° laminates were prepared only for the first two cure cycles.

Out of each 200 x 200 mm laminate 6 specimens for microscopic examination were cut from different laminate zones as well as a variable number (6 to 10) of tensile samples according to ASTM D 3039.

Cure cycle	Laminate	Orientation	Starting temperature	Starting pressure	Heating rate	Time to reach cure temperature	Cure temperature	Pressure increase		Cure pressure	Permanence at cure temperature	Cooling
			(°C)	(MPa)	(°C/min)	(min)		(°C)	(min)			
I	A-B	0°	20	0.25	2.1	50	125	50	125	0.75	75	slow
	A-B	±45°										
II	C-D	0°	20	0.25	7.5	14	125	14	125	0.75	60	fast
	C-D	±45°										
III	E-F	±45°	20	0.25	2.1	50	125	50	125	1.50	60	slow
IV	G	±45°	20	0.15	7.5	14	125	34	125	0.75	60	fast
V	H	±45°	20	0	7.5	14	125	--	--	0	60	fast

Table I - Cure cycle parameters.

Fig. 1 - Cure cycles temperature and pressure versus time.

RESULTS

Mechanical tests

In table II are reported for 0° laminates the average value, standard deviation and parameter of scatter of ultimate tensile strength, σ_u , and Young modulus, E, such as were obtained in a previous work (2).

In table III are reported for $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates the same statistical parameters of ultimate strength, "knee stress" (*), and Young modulus as obtained in (2).

Microscopic examinations

0° specimens. Photomicrographs reported in figure 2 show the typical structures of 0° specimens from laminates A to D. Specimens from A and B (cure cycle I) exhibit a low, scarcely scattered porosity and a few large voids (figs. 2a and 2b). In specimens from C and D (cure cycle II) only a small, rather scanty porosity is present (figs. 2c and 2d).

$\pm 45^\circ$ specimens. In figure 3 the photomicrographs of $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens from laminates A to H are reported.

In photomicrographs 3a and 3b, relative to laminates A and B (cure cycle I), a few large interlaminar voids are observed as well as a medium size porosity in resin rich areas and a small porosity scattered among the fibres.

(*) The stress - time graphs of $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile specimens showed, after an initial linear increase, a stretch with decreasing slope typical of a pseudo - plastic behaviour of the material. This stretch is what we called "knee". For "knee" stress evaluation criterion see (2).

Cure cycle	Laminate	Ultimate tensile strength			Young modulus		
		Mean value (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Parameter of scatter (%)	Mean value (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Parameter of scatter (%)
I	A	731	29.8	4.1	45100	2880	6.4
I	B	674	25.6	3.8	41810	1510	3.6
II	C	738	21.1	2.9	45960	2860	6.2
II	D	703	24.6	3.5	45150	1400	3.1

Table II - 0° laminates: average value, standard deviation and parameter of scatter for the mechanical characteristics.

Cure cycle	Laminate	Ultimate tensile strength			Knee stress % of σ_{ult}	Young modulus		
		Mean value (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Parameter of scatter (%)		Mean value (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Parameter of scatter (%)
I	A	154	7.7	5.0	63	18590	1830	9.8
I	B	150	6.3	4.2	63	17120	1540	9.0
II	C	157	5.2	3.3	61	18330	1140	6.2
II	D	149	4.4	3.0	62	18400	1940	10.5
III	E	157	4.8	3.1	64	17880	1060	5.9
III	F	161	5.4	3.4	65	17970	870	4.8
IV	G	156	3.4	2.2	60	16500	860	5.2
V	H	80	11.1	13.9	87	10670	540	5.1

Table III - ±45° laminates: average value, standard deviation and parameter of scatter for the mechanical characteristics.

In the specimens from laminates C and D (cure cycle II) large voids were not found. In laminate C a more or less scattered small porosity is observed (fig. 3c). Laminate D specimens exhibit a not very diffuse small size porosity (fig.3d).

Also laminate E specimens (cure cycle III) (fig. 3e) evidence a scanty porosity of small size. Laminate F specimens (cure cycle III) display in certain areas a higher porosity given by several small and medium voids and elsewhere a more diffuse porosity of smaller size (fig. 3f).

Specimens from laminate G (cure cycle IV) (fig. 3g) show a very high and diffuse porosity consisting of large voids (though smaller than the voids observed in laminate A and B specimens) and small and medium voids scattered among the fibres and in resin areas. As a whole, specimens from laminate G exhibit a higher porosity than those preceding.

Finally, specimens from laminate H (cure cycle V) display a very high

Fig. 2 - Structures of 0° specimens (100 x). (a) laminate A - cure cycle I; (b) laminate B - cure cycle I; (c) laminate C - cure cycle II; (d) laminate D - cure cycle II.

porosity determined by very large flaws between laminae and by large voids among the fibres and in resin areas (fig. 3h).

In order to evaluate the void content of the laminates under examination, the following procedure was adopted. A point-count grid, marked on clear plastic, was applied to photomicrographs obtained from each specimen examined and the number of points, N_p , that fell in the void areas was counted. By dividing N_p by the total number of test points N_g , the ratio $N_p/N_g = V_v$ is obtained, where V_v is the percentage void volume content of the composite structure (3).

In table IV the average values of void content measurements are reported for each laminate.

ANALYSIS

It can be noticed from tables II and III that there are no meaningful differences in the mechanical tensile properties of specimens from 0° and ±45° laminates (in the latter case at least for the first seven laminates) obtained with different cure cycles. The only exception being laminate G elastic modulus, but this occurrence was not considered of real consequence in (2).

Laminate H (±45°) was the only one whose very low mechanical properties undoubtedly revealed a wrong cure cycle. But this cycle (cure cycle V) was so grossly abnormal that it could be recognized by simple visual examination of the laminate without resorting to mechanical tests.

Therefore data obtained from simple tensile tests are not sufficient or

Fig. 3 - Structures of $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens (100 x). (a) lam. A - cycle I; (b) lam. B - cycle I; (c) lam. C - cycle II; (d) lam. D - cycle II; (e) lam. E - cycle III; (f) lam. F - cycle III; (g) lam. G - cycle IV; (h) lam. H - cycle V.

Orientation	Cure cycle	Laminate	Porosity V_v (%)
0°	I	A	2.3
	I	B	2.3
	II	C	0.5
	II	D	0.6
±45°	I	A	2.7
	I	B	2.6
	II	C	0.6
	II	D	0.6
	III	E	0.8
	III	F	0.9
	IV	G	4.4
	V	H	26.0

Table IV - Average values of void contents.

sufficiently meaningful in order to discriminate casual or intentional variations of the composite cure cycle (obviously within certain limits).

On the other hand microscopic examinations evidence marked differences in porosity content of specimens obtained with different cure cycles, whereas laminates cured with the same cycle show similar structures (tab. IV). Such differences can be correlated to cure cycle conditions.

With reference to cure cycle I (fig. 1 and tab. I), it can be assumed that in laminates A and B, both 0° and ±45°, the resin, at the moment of pressure increase, was already in a stage of advanced gelification having attained the temperature of 125 °C after a very slow heating. The applied pressure was consequently insufficient to expel from the laminate all the air and the resin volatile products set free during heating. As a consequence residual porosity in the composite was high.

In laminates C and D, both 0° and ±45°, fabricated with cure cycle II, pressure increase occurred again at 125 °C though after a rapid heating. Thus the resin was pressurized while still very fluid. Most of the entrapped air could therefore be evacuated leaving a very low residual porosity in the laminates.

In the case of laminates E and F (cure cycle III), pressure is doubled (1.5 MPa) while temperature increases slowly. It may be supposed that with such cure cycle a higher amount of voids were eliminated because of the high pressure value though the resin was already very viscous (slow heating) at the moment of pressure increase. Porosity must therefore be lower than in laminates A and B (cycle I) and higher than in laminates C and D (cycle II) (tab. IV).

In the case of laminate G, though a very rapid heating was employed, a pressure of 0.75 MPa was applied 20 minutes after the moment the temperature of 125 °C had been reached. The high residual porosity is therefore ascribable to the late pressure application with respect to the resin gelification process.

Laminate H needs no comment because, as pressure was kept extremely low during the entire curing (cycle V), the enormous porosity content and the very poor interlaminar linkage were obviously inevitable.

CONCLUSIONS

Mechanical tests and microscopic examinations have produced diverging informations. While tensile tests results did not prove capable of discriminating structural variations induced by different cure cycles in laminates with equal fibre orientations, microscopic examinations evidenced significant differences in void content correlatable to the interdependencies among cure cycle characteristic parameters (time, temperature, pressure).

Even if the structural variations induced by cure cycle deviating from the optimum cycle do not influence the composite static properties, they cannot but influence the composite fatigue properties or its environment resistance or its creep resistance, particularly in the case of angle-ply composites (4) (5) (6).

More profound investigations are therefore necessary than those allowed by simple tensile tests.

In the present work the authors resorted to microscopic examinations that, however, on one hand are time-consuming and require specialized personnel and on the other do not produce information on the resin curing and on the fibre-matrix interface properties.

The need is felt to develop a testing technique being at the same time simple, real-time and sufficiently sensitive to material structural variations.

Acoustic emission seems to be a very promising testing technique for the study of composite material properties and the authors, on the basis of preceding experiences (1), suggest and propose to investigate its applicability to the solution of the problems evidenced in the present paper (7).

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REFERENCES

- (1) Crivelli Visconti, I., Teti, R. and Langone, V., "Application of Acoustic Emission Techniques for the Investigation of Mechanical Behaviour of GRP Composite Materials", *Advances in Composite Materials, Proc. of the 3rd Int. Conf. on Comp. Mat. (ICCM III)*, Paris, 26-29 Aug. 1980, pp. 944-958.
- (2) Di Ilio, A., Crivelli Visconti, I. and Teti, R., "Proprietà meccaniche di compositi vetro-resina fabbricati con diversi cicli di polimerizzazione" *La Meccanica Italiana*, n. 164, luglio-agosto 1982.
- (3) Hilliard, J.E., in Quantitative Microscopy, Edited by R.T. DeHoff and F.N. Rhines, Mc Graw - Hill, 1968.
- (4) Crivelli Visconti, I., "Design of continuous fibre composite structures", *USA-Italy Joint Symp. on Comp. Mat.*, Capri, Italy, 15-19 June 1981.
- (5) Crivelli Visconti, I., Materiali Compositi - Tecnologie e Progettazione, Ed. Tamburini, Milano, 1975.
- (6) Apicella, A., Nicolais, L., Astarita, G. and Drioli, E., "Effect of Thermal History on Water Sorption, Elastic Properties and the Glass Transition of Epoxy Resins", *Polymer*, Sept. 1979, vol. 20, pp. 1143-1148.
- (7) Teti, R., Di Ilio, A., Crivelli Visconti, I., "Fabrication Cycle Influence on the Acoustic Emission Response of GFRP Composites", *ICCM IV, Tokio, 1982*.